

MINING THE MINES' FOSSIL COLLECTIONS I: THE EARLIEST- COLLECTED *LAGARODUS* FROM NORTH AMERICA

by Wayne Itano

For several years, WIPS volunteers have been helping to identify and catalog the fossil specimens in the collections of the Colorado School of Mines (CSM) Geology Museum. The specimens are mostly in cardboard boxes stacked several deep on open shelves in a warehouse on the CSM campus. Thanks to the cataloging project, it is possible to search a computer database to locate specimens of interest (at least some of them). This is a work in progress.

Since I have had a long-term interest in the sharks from the Pennsylvanian Minturn Formation at McCoy, Colorado, I asked Dennis Gertenbach, who has been coordinating the WIPS volunteers, whether there were any McCoy shark specimens in the CSM collections. He found three McCoy shark teeth and sent photos. Two were *Petalodus*, which is common and not of much interest. The

third one looked like a less common genus, called *Lagarodus*.

The CSM *Lagarodus* specimen

I visited the CSM collections on April 14, 2012, which was a WIPS volunteer day, to have a closer look at the *Lagarodus* tooth and other specimens. Figure 1 shows the labels that are associated with the McCoy shark teeth. Even though the three teeth do not belong to the same species, they had been given a common number, 11343, and were distinguished by letters (A, B, and C) written on the specimens. The handwritten label at the upper left of Fig. 1 gives the information that the teeth were found at "Station 7, McCoy, Colo." by "H & B" on October 24, 1927. The old, typewriter-written label on the lower left of Fig. 1 expands the names of the collectors to "Higgins & B." Note that the horizon is given as Hermosa, rather than Minturn, since the Minturn Formation had not yet been named in 1927. Also note that this label is marked "Texas Production Co. Paleontological Laboratory," not "Colorado School of Mines." Apparently these specimens were transferred from the Texas Production Company to the CSM at some time after 1927. The new, computer-generated label on the right of Fig. 1 expands the names of the collectors to "Higgins & Breckenridge." The person who made the new label must have had access to information that is not on the old labels. It would be nice to know where "Station 7" was. I don't know whether any field notes associated with these specimens are still preserved.

Fig. 1. Labels associated with the shark teeth from McCoy, Colorado in the CSM collections.

Specimens 11343A and 11343B are *Petalodus*, probably *Petalodus ohioensis* Safford, by far the most common shark tooth found at McCoy. I recognized specimen 11343C as *Lagarodus specularis* (Trautschold). Figure 2 shows the occlusal surface (the surface used to crush food). Note the pattern of small depressions on the surface. This is characteristic of *Lagarodus* and some other kinds of shark teeth. Figure 3 is a lateral view. The sharp bend on the left side is characteristic of the *angustus* morphotype (shape) of *Lagarodus specularis*. (More about morphotypes later.)

What was *Lagarodus*?

Lagarodus was a chondrichthyan, distantly related to modern sharks. It had a flattened, pavement-like dentition, like some modern rays. The teeth had different shapes, depending on their position. At one time, teeth now believed to belong to a single species were assigned to three separate species, *Psammodus specularis*, *Psammodus angustus*, and *Psammodus cubicus*. The generic name was later changed to *Lagarodus*. For a time, all three “species” were united under one name, *Lagarodus angustus* (Romanowsky). Recently, Lebedev (2008) changed the species name to *Lagarodus specularis* (Trautschold) for reasons having to do with the nonvalidity of Romanowsky’s species. The three former species are now called the *specularis*, *angustus*, and *cubicus* morphotypes (shapes) of the single species *Lagarodus specularis*. Lebedev named two more morphotypes, called “accessory” and “orobranchial.” Since only isolated teeth, never an articulated dentition,

have been found, the way in which the various morphotypes of teeth fitted together is unknown. Three very different arrangements have been proposed recently (Elliott, Irmis, Hansen, & Olsen, 2004; Hansen, 1986; Lebedev, 2008). *Lagarodus specularis* is the only recognized species of the genus *Lagarodus*.

Specimens of *Lagarodus* were first found in Russia (Trautschold, 1874), and it appears that they are relatively abundant in some of the Pennsylvanian deposits in the region around Moscow. Figures 4 and 5 show some specimens of the *angustus* and *specularis* morphotypes of *Lagarodus specularis* respectively. The specimens are in the collections of the Natural History Museum, London, and are from Myachkovo, near Moscow, from the Middle Pennsylvanian. Note the graceful nineteenth century writing of the labels. I took these photographs on a visit to London in December 2011. The *specularis* and *angustus* morphotypes are the ones most commonly found. The *specularis* morphotype has a convex occlusal surface and an outline that is rhomboidal or lozenge-shaped. The *angustus* morphotype is roughly rectangular in outline with an occlusal surface that bends down sharply on one side, as seen in Fig. 3.

There are reports, based on very fragmentary material, of *Lagarodus* from the Mississippian of Belgium (de Koninck, 1878) and the Pennsylvanian of Greenland (Bendix-Almgreen, 1975), but it is difficult to say for sure whether these teeth represent the same species or even the same genus as the Pennsylvanian specimens from Russia.

Fig. 2. Top view of the CSM *Lagarodus* tooth from McCoy, showing the occlusal (biting) surface. Note the small depressions or pores. These are characteristic of *Lagarodus*. The specimen number 11343C is written on the surface. The length is 13.5 mm. **Fig. 3.** Side view of the *Lagarodus* tooth from McCoy. The occlusal surface curves up gradually to the left, then sharply down. The sharp downward curvature is characteristic of the *angustus* morphotype of *Lagarodus specularis*.

The affinities of *Lagarodus* are obscure. It was originally placed with the psammodonts, an extinct group of chondrichthyans having flat, pavement-like teeth. Psammodonts were probably closer to modern chimaerids (ratfish) than to modern sharks and rays (elasmobranchs). However, Lebedev (2008) places *Lagarodus* with the elasmobranchs, based on the arrangement of teeth in rows and series and on the presence of enameloid on unworn crown surfaces, in contrast to *Psammodus*.

Other *Lagarodus* in North America

Despite extensive collecting of chondrichthyan teeth from Pennsylvanian deposits since the mid-nineteenth century, *Lagarodus* was not reported from North America until Michael Hansen of the Ohio Geological Survey reported a few teeth of *Lagarodus specularis* from the Pennsylvanian of Ohio in his Ph.D. thesis (Hansen, 1986). The tooth found in 1927 by Higgins and Breckenridge was not recognized until now.

Junius Henderson (after whom the Henderson Building of the University of Colorado Museum is named) collected fossils from McCoy in the early 1900s, but the only vertebrate remains found were *Petalodus* teeth and *Ctenacanthus* finspines. John Chronic and Calvin Stevens of the University of Colorado collected at McCoy in the 1950s (Stevens, 1958), but found no *Lagarodus* teeth. In the early 1980s, Martin Lockley and Karen Houck, then at the University of Colorado at Denver, found several *Lagarodus* teeth at McCoy, which were identified as such by Michael Hansen (Lockley, 1984). Some of the Colorado *Lagarodus* teeth were described in Hansen's Ph.D. thesis. Other *Lagarodus* teeth from McCoy were found by amateurs, including WIPS members Jordan Sawdo, the late Bill Bateman, Doug Nelson, and Steve Thompson. I plan to study the McCoy specimens in more detail and to compare them to the Russian specimens I photographed in London. Although they look very similar at first sight, there could be differences. Oleg Lebedev points out that the crown of the CSM specimen is somewhat more rounded than is typical of *Lagarodus specularis*.

Since the Ohio and Colorado discoveries, a few *Lagarodus* teeth have been reported from Middle Pennsylvanian deposits in Arizona (Elliott et al.,

Fig. 4. Six teeth of the *angustus* morphotype of *Lagarodus specularis* from Russia. Scale is in cm.

Fig. 5. Five teeth of the *specularis* morphotype of *Lagarodus specularis* from Russia.

2004), New Mexico (Zidek & Kietzke, 1993), and Kansas (Hamm & Cicimurri, 2005).

From the limited number of known occurrences, it appears that *Lagarodus* was widespread but not particularly abundant, and was probably limited to a rather brief stratigraphic range in the Middle Pennsylvanian.

False *Lagarodus*

A Web search for “*Lagarodus*” turns up fossil dealers claiming to have *Lagarodus* teeth to sell. I have found that these teeth, except for those from

Russia, are not *Lagarodus*. The false *Lagarodus* are usually from the Mississippian of Indiana. They may be *Orodus*, *Helodus*, *Psephodus*, or some unidentified helodontiform or cochliodontiform chondrichthyans.

Who were Higgins and Breckenridge?

I have been unable to identify Breckenridge. The old label listing the names as “Higgins & B.” indicates that Breckenridge was the junior partner in the project, since his full name was not given. I have uncovered a likely candidate for the Higgins listed on the specimen labels. Daniel Franklin Higgins (1882-1930) was a geologist with very wide-ranging interests. He wrote several scientific papers, including some on Front Range geology. He taught at several colleges and universities. He did work for the US Geological Survey in Alaska and for a gold mine in Korea. According to an obituary that appeared in the *Journal of Paleontology* (Plummer, 1930), D. F. Higgins was, from 1927 to 1929, in charge of “the geologic work in the Rocky Mountain Division for The Texas Company with headquarters in Denver.” There is a discrepancy with the specimen label in Fig. 1, on which is printed “Texas Production Co.” The Texas Company, now called Texaco, is not the same as the Texas Production Company, but this is likely just an error on the part of the obituary writer.

Significance and lessons

What can be learned from the belated recognition of a *Lagarodus* tooth in the CSM collections? For one thing, rare specimens do turn up, even in well-collected localities. One shouldn't assume that everything has already been found by others. Rare and unusual specimens should be brought to the attention of specialists who can evaluate their significance. Had a specialist in Paleozoic sharks seen the McCoy *Lagarodus* tooth at any time prior to Michael Hansen's work in the 1980s, the discovery of the first occurrence of the genus outside of Europe might have warranted a publication in, for example, the *Journal of Paleontology*. Instead, specimen CSM 11343C is of historical interest, but does not add much to our scientific knowledge. A final lesson is that detailed locality information should always be recorded permanently. We know that the specimen was found in the vicinity of McCoy, Colorado, but we don't know the precise location and stratigraphic level of “Station 7.” If we can determine

this, we might be able to determine whether this particular tooth is younger or older than others of the same species that have been found at McCoy.

Acknowledgments

I thank Dennis Gertenbach and Beth Simmons for providing access to the CSM collections. I thank Martha Richter for being my host at the Natural History Museum, London, where I was able to examine *Lagarodus* specimens from Russia. I thank Oleg Lebedev of the Palaeontological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences for comments on the manuscript.

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TRILOBITE TALES

VOLUME 30, NUMBER 6
SEPTEMBER 2012

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Stegosaurus, the Colorado State Fossil,
Art © Shannon S. Yeager

SEPTEMBER PROGRAM: ANNUAL SHOW & TELL

TUESDAY, September 11, 2012, 7 p.m.
Denver Museum of Nature & Science
IMAX Theatre Lobby

September is a season of change as the leaves begin to turn gold and whisper promises of cooler weather. So goes our September WIPS meeting. We will be kicking off the new season with a show and tell session in the IMAX theater lobby rather than the usual lecture in Ricketson auditorium. We are also meeting a week later than usual, due to some scheduling challenges.

Grab those special summer finds and come show them off to your friends and fellow members. Garner "oohs and aaahs" from your fellow paleo-minded-friends. Or, bring in that fossil that you're struggling to identify or still trying to figure out what it is and see if you can stump the paleontologists!

Even if you've not been able to get out in the field, we know it will be interesting to see what others have found, so hope to see you there on Tuesday September 11th.

